

Collaboration In Early Intervention In Saudi Arabia: Reality And Barriers

Mohamad Adnan Bukhary

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 19, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Early Childhood Special Education, Collaboration, Barriers</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5528851</p>	<p><i>This study aims to investigate the reality of collaboration in early childhood education between Saudi parents and professionals, and the hurdles that parents encounter with regard to this. A mixed-method approach was employed (quantitative and qualitative). An online survey was conducted among parents of children with disabilities (n=272) comprising 25 questions distributed over five domains. These were (knowledge of collaboration practices, communication, commitment, equality, trust, and respect). Interviews were conducted (n=6) to investigate the reality of collaboration and the barriers parents face in this process. The study found that parents have some understanding of collaboration practices, and that professionals respected their cultural values. Some parents reported that they feel professionals have few skills in the areas of commitment, trust and respect. They also considered that professionals need more training to implement collaboration more effectively. Based on these findings, several recommendations for future practices and areas of research are provided.</i></p>

Introduction

It is said that parents are the most powerful catalyst for improving the educational standards established for their children with disabilities (Bang, 2018; Friend & Cook, 2014). Several studies have confirmed the significant role parents play in enhancing their children's academic performance (Simpson & Envy, 2015; Kyzar et al., 2019; Sabol et al., 2018). Other studies linked parents' involvement in their children's education with many positive outcomes which include the following: increased concentration toward classwork, reduction in behavioral challenges, improvement in student attendance, enhancement of school programs, the overall school ecosystem and increases in parent-student long-term educational planning. Furthermore, students are more sensitive to common messages like the significance of education, hard work, innovative thinking and empathy for others (Lohman et al., 2018). Laws require parents and teachers to collaborate in order to enhance the educational outcomes of children with disabilities. For example, the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) (2004) outlines the obligations of educators to families in educational settings (Viviani, 2016; Yell, 2019). Great efforts have certainly been made to urge the parties to the educational process to cooperate in order to achieve the interests of children with disabilities. However, the actual picture may differ in a practical aspect if we wish to perceive the reality from different corners and parents' perspectives toward the nature of their involvement. Furthermore, their collaboration with the educational professionals in early childhood special education (ECSE) should be considered. Moreover, two crucial variables on attaining collaboration must be questioned: barriers to collaboration and aspects that promote it.

Problem Statement and Questions

Despite the considerable progress in promoting collaboration and inclusivity in the Saudi education sector over the previous years, the Saudi Government still needs to make a greater effort to support inclusivity and collaborative initiatives. (Murry & Alqahtani, 2015). This is because it was proven that collaboration between parents and educational professionals promotes the academic outcomes and the mental health of children with disabilities, especially in early intervention (Simpson & Envy, 2015). Despite the huge endeavors made in providing high-quality centers for special education, the inclusion of children with disabilities in general education schools and the reform enacted in response to demands for a specific curriculum for special needs education, the gap between parents' actual participation in early intervention (IE) and the nature of the collaboration between them and the professionals remain underestimated. However, parents encounter various obstacles which limit their participation in early intervention and collaboration with professionals. This study is a part of a large research which intended to address this issue in an attempt to bridge the gap and accomplish the best interests of children with disabilities by answering the following questions:

- What is the reality of early intervention collaboration between Saudi parents and professionals?

- Are there significant differences in Saudi Arabian parents' perceptions of collaboration across demographic variables (e.g. gender, family income, the severity of a child's disability and the family's level of educational achievement)?
- What variables hinder parent-professional collaboration?

Literature Review

An Overview of Collaboration in ECSE in KSA

Collaboration pertains to how effectively people who have legal custody of a child with disabilities collaborate with education professionals. It entails teamwork between custodians and professionals who rely on and respect each other's expertise, familiarity with the child, and resources. When properly conducted, its efforts directly benefit children with disabilities and indirectly benefit the other stakeholders such as parents and professionals (Turnbull et al., 2015). It also works to induce children with disabilities to improve their learning outcomes and to support their social skills development (Majoko, 2017). Saudi Arabia fosters collaboration between families and educational professionals through its legal framework. The Saudi Regulations of Special Education Programs and Institutes (RSEPI, 2001) includes stipulations concerning these matters (Dare et al., 2017). Furthermore, it outlines the different rights and responsibilities of stakeholders in the provision of education services (Alquraini, 2013; Dare et al., 2017). However, there are no explicit legal provisions that stipulate how the collaboration should be implemented between parties to the educational process which may constitute a hurdle in understanding the scope of collaboration between both parties. Moreover, Saudi Arabia's jurisdictions that govern these processes vary in reality, as one school in a specific region might operate under a law that requires parents' participation in developing an Individual Family Service Plan (IFSP), whereas another school in the same district may be governed by a policy that requires only teachers to develop IFSPs.

Early childhood education in Saudi Arabia (Alquraini, 2013) included children between three and eight years old. The Ministry of Education has emphasized the importance of the inclusion of children with disabilities in early childhood services by providing two special education classroom systems within general education schools where students with disabilities are educated either completely separately from their typical peers or by partial inclusion which is limited to specific social or academic activities (Al-Zoubi & Rahman, 2015). Furthermore, it employed counselors and special education teachers to facilitate their inclusion in the general education setting. Nonetheless, the Saudi education system does not require schools to invite parents to be a part of their children's educational experience. This is again problematic as collaborative practices are considered beneficial for children, parents, and for the community. It should be borne in mind that the beliefs held by educators about family involvement are likely to affect the quality of relationships forged between them (Clough & Nutbrown, 2019; Simpson & Envy, 2015). Several researchers have supported this concept with findings indicating that children who experience adequate family involvement during their educational experience tend to exhibit improved social skills and behavior (Friend & Cook, 2014). Such children also tend to achieve higher grades and test scores compared to their peers who did not receive the same level of collaboration.

Another important fact is that there are only three high-quality public early intervention (EI) centers in Saudi Arabia near the major population canters of Riyadh, Makkah, and Dammam. The activities in these centers are very comprehensive and include programs that aim to develop the social, emotional, physical and mental development traits of children with disabilities (Hadidi & Al Khateeb, 2020). They also work to identify children who are eligible for services, planning programs, providing services based on their needs (Blackmore et al., 2016), tracking progress, and transition programs — all of which are considered the main components of early intervention. Despite the high quality of these centers, they operate independently, and there is no collaboration or sharing of metadata between them (Felimban, 2019). Moreover, many private early intervention centers around the country provide many services such as (speech-language therapy, occupational and physical therapy services, psychological counseling, and health services and so on). Furthermore, children with severe disabilities are taught in these centers. (Murry & Alqahtani, 2015; Dare et al., 2017). This may constitute a heavy financial burden on parents' shoulders; in fact, few Saudi centers allow parents to be involved in the educational process, particularly fathers. Despite the efforts made in this regard, these centers lack a systematic framework for distributing educational resources, meaning that the rights and roles of parents during early intervention implementations are limited, and that the quality and availability of early intervention (EI) services in the kingdom are also limited (Almalki, 2013). Compliance with meeting parental rights is often restricted to simply informing them of their child's diagnosis rather than referring them for additional services offering accommodation. Similarly, the formal services offered in this context may involve the provision of financial assistance and an increase in access to a mobility aid. One of the greatest challenges for early childhood educators in collaboration is the development of support systems which help to collaborative relationships (Young, 2017). This is the case that when families and education professionals collaborate effectively, there will be greater awareness of family needs and cultural values which may have long-term positive impacts on children (Majoko, 2017).

Effective Guidelines for Collaboration

Collaboration has not been applied as effectively as evidence-based practices require because there are often misconceptions associated with this amongst parties (Kyzar, Mueller et al., 2019). Therefore, Blue-Banning et al. (2004) specified guidelines that ensure collaboration efforts are effective and that they help collaborators to understand the expectations of the collaboration process. The first principle, **Commitment**, is a sort of clear guarantee or tacit agreement developed between the parties regarding their obligation and pledge to be faithful to the best interests of the child (Blue-Banning et al., 2004). The second is **Communication** which should be easily understood and convey a message clearly to others. Information should be presented in a manner that is empathic and respectful to all parties involved (Blue-Banning et al., 2004). These exchanges should be honest but also tactful, so none of the parties is offended. These interactions should also be frequent and well-coordinated. The third principle is **Equality** which requires that parties are treated equally at all stages, including decision-making, diagnosis and the delivery of services (Blue-Banning et al., 2004). **Respect** indicates that all parties should consider collaboration to be a partnership where other members are equally respected. Professionals must value the child and refrain from engaging in any type of discriminatory attitude. Furthermore, involved parties are required to be respectful and non-judgmental when they interact with each other. The fifth principle focuses on acquiring **Skills** as all educational professionals should be fully trained and well equipped to handle their responsibilities. The last principle is **Trust**, and educators and professionals should undoubtedly be perceived as dependable in order to establish a relationship with families and children that is built on trust. Steps must be taken by education providers to create a comfortable and safe environment for all students, especially those with disabilities, because child safety in the learning environment is the highest priority (Blue-Banning et al., 2004).

What factors promote or hinder parent-professional collaboration?

Collaboration between families and educators is regarded as an essential strategy for improving the learning outcomes of children with disabilities. However, a lack of collaboration among them may lead to poor learning outcomes and limitations in the provision of early intervention services. As mentioned previously, the effectiveness of using collaborative strategies is dependent upon stakeholder knowledge and the use of these strategies (Friend & Cook, 2014).

Training is another aspect that promotes collaboration in the inclusive learning environment because it prepares professionals to be good collaborators by allowing them to lead or manage collaborative learning activities (Brock et al., 2017) which later facilitate the creation of a healthy learning environment in the special education setting where teachers, children, and parents cooperate to improve a child's learning outcomes. Training also prepares special education teachers to successfully assess a child's learning needs and to identify any shortfalls in the current practices. Training programs also allow professionals to develop a framework for involving parents in their children's education in a manner that does not distract from children's normal learning processes. Training parents in collaboration can remove many hurdles for children with disabilities, such as by encouraging desired behaviours (Schultzal, 2016). Therefore, standardized guidelines must be set so that educators can present and evaluate an established curriculum with parents about early intervention and effective collaboration with their children's teachers (Meadan&Daczewitz, 2014).

Despite advances in removing the barriers that prevent children with special needs from receiving an excellent education, numerous factors continue to prevent educational stakeholders from effectively collaborating with one another, negatively impacting the educational development of children with disabilities such as:

- Lack of a proper and clear definition of collaboration (Hernandez, 2013);
- Lack of a correct understanding of the role of collaboration in affecting educational outcomes (Blue-Banning et al., 2004);
- The reality of special education influences the success of collaboration in early intervention (Paananen et al., 2015); for example, funding may influence the quality of collaboration in many special education settings (Paananen et al., 2015).
- The unwillingness of some educational professionals to embrace the concept of collaboration (Hamilton-Jones & Vail, 2014) due to the ambivalence and significant difficulties they may face when employing collaboration in early intervention and may be due to individualistic culture (Hernandez, 2013).
- Collaboration among education parties may be affected by human dynamics.
- The mandated testing of children with special needs negatively impacts collaboration with professionals in early childhood special education (Hopkins et al., 2017).

Method

Research Methods

A mixed-methods approach was employed using both qualitative and quantitative methods by distributing a questionnaire to 272 participants and conducting interviews with six parents of children with disabilities.

Sample

The sample of this study comprised 272 Saudi parents who have children with disabilities enrolled in early intervention programs in Abha, Dammam, Jeddah, Mecca, Medina, and Ta'if. (Female=196; Male = 76). Only six parents participated in the interviews.

Research Instruments and Procedures

Two instruments were used in this study, a survey designed by the researcher with 25 items dispersed across five areas. It was administered electronically to (272) parents of children with disabilities using the WSU Qualtrics online survey platform. It assessed five major areas, namely (commitment, communication, knowledge of collaboration, equality and respect). Open-ended questions in semi-structured interviews were employed to collect data from six Saudi parents from the study sample. For ethical consideration, the study procedures were reviewed by the Department of Special Education at Washington State University, and Institutional Review Board approval (IRB) was obtained. Moreover, approval was obtained by the Ministry of Education in KSA represented by the Department of Planning and Development to circulate the questionnaire to the target sample. The study participants were assured that all data would be strictly confidential and would be used only for scientific research purposes. Figure 1 depicts a summary of the procedures and methods used in both study instruments, including (instruments, validity, reliability and analysis methods).

Figure 1. A summary of the employed procedures and methods

Results and Discussion

Demographics of Participants

Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS statistical software. Descriptive analysis, independent sample t-test and one-way ANOVA were used to determine whether there were any statistically significant differences between the means of two or more independent groups and to test the relationship between the variables (see Table 1).

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage of Demographic Information Within the Sample (n =272)

Demographic Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Female	196	72.1%
Male	76	27.9%
Education Level		
Elementary	2	.7%
Secondary	47	17.3%

Undergraduate	170	62.5%
Graduate	53	19.5%
Income		
< 5000 SAR	33	12.1%
5001 - 10000 SAR	94	34.6%
10001 -15000 SAR	58	21.3%
> 15000 SAR	84	30.9%
No response	3	1.1%
Severity of Disability		
Mild	89	32.7%
Moderate	154	56.6%
Severe	29	10.7%
Type of EI Center		
Governmental	123	45.2%
Private	149	54.8%
No Intervention Center	0	0%

The demographic data of the respondents (n = 272) shows that the majority of the respondents who constitute (72.1%) of the respondents are females, of which (62.5%) are undergraduates and (19.5%) graduates (19.5%). Also, (34.6) reported a monthly income of (5001-10.000 SR), where and of (30.9%) with income (< 15.000 RS), only (12.1%) earn (< 5000 SR). Regarding the child's degree of disability, the responses show indicated that (32.7%) have a mild disability, (56.6%) moderate and (10.7) severe disabilities. A little more than over half (54.8%) of the respondents enrolled their child in a private early childhood service center, and the remaining respondents (45.2%) indicated that their child attends a government-run center.

Collaboration Practices

Descriptive analysis was used to investigate parents' perception toward the reality of collaboration practices in EI using a 5-point Likert scale (see Table 2).

Table 2: Items in Knowledge of Practices

Rank	Item	Strongly Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat Agree	Strongly Agree
1	I have sufficient knowledge about collaboration in ECSE.	2.6%	3.7 %	16.9 %	36.0 %	40.8%
2	I understand the purposes of collaboration in ECSE.	0.0%	2.9%	8.8%	34.6%	53.7%
3	I have knowledge of collaboration practices	1.1%	3.7%	9.9%	34.2%	51.1%
4	I know collaboration extended to deliver interventions & other forms of collaboration.	0.4%	1.5%	8.5%	24.6%	65.1%
5	I can decide if the collaboration is beneficial to my child and me.	0.7%	2.2%	5.9%	30.1%	61.0%

All the respondents chose "strongly agreed" with Items 1-5 indicating that they understood what collaboration entails, while 91.1% of respondents reported their ability to decide whether collaboration is beneficial to their child. Moreover, (89.7%) of the respondents stated that they "somewhat agreed" or "strongly agreed" with Item 4. When respondents were asked if they "have sufficient knowledge of collaboration," "can understand the purposes of collaboration in ECSE" as well as "knowing collaboration practices" their responses were "somewhat agree" or "strongly agree" with the ratio of 76.8%, 88.3% and 85.3% respectively.

Communication Skills

Communication skills of the professionals were investigated using a 5-point Likert scale to measure the responses regarding the items 6-12. (see Table 3).

Table 3: Items Related to Communication

Rank	Survey Item	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Very Frequently	Always
------	-------------	-------	--------	--------------	-----------------	--------

6	Professionals communicate clearly.	4.0%	17.6%	39.7 %	22.8 %	15.8%
7	Professionals allow adequate time to share information with me.	4.8%	18%	41.2%	21.3%	14.7%
8	Professionals answer questions sufficiently.	7.0%	13.6%	37.9%	26.5%	15.1%
9	Professionals are open and are good listeners throughout discussions about my child's strengths and needs.	5.1%	10.7%	36.8%	26.8%	20.6%
10	Professionals communicate positively during meetings.	5.9%	11.4%	32.4%	30.5%	19.9%
11	Professionals respect our cultural values.	5.5%	5.9%	25.9%	36.8%	26.5%
12	Overall, I am satisfied with professionals' communication skills.	10.3%	10.7%	29.8%	26.8%	22.4%

As shown in Table (3), respondents selected "occasionally" to express the clarity of professionals' communication, adequate time for sharing information, answering parents' questions, openness, positivity and their satisfaction with professionals' communication skills with percentages of 39.7%, 41.2%, 37.9%, 36.8%, 32.4% and 29.8% respectively. Contrastingly, they chose "very frequently" to express professionals' respect for parents' culture 36.8%.

Commitment:

The following table shows the respondents' viewpoints on the reality of professionals' commitment using a 5-point Likert scale.

Table 4: *Items Related to Commitment*

Rank	Survey	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Very Frequently	Always
13	Professionals demonstrate their knowledge of effective collaboration.	6.3%	13.2%	34.6%	29.4%	16.5%
14	Professionals are consistently available to my child and family.	10.3%	14.7%	33.8%	28.7%	12.5%
15	Professionals seem to be working toward the same, agreed-upon goals.	5.1%	11.4%	33.8%	31.2%	18.4%
16	Professionals are willing to train me in how to provide services in different environments.	9.9%	16.2%	29.4%	25.7%	18.8%
17	Professionals adequately share information with me regarding my child's disability.	8.5%	8.5%	35.3%	29.4%	18.4%

According to the data, most of the responses were "occasionally" and "very frequently". In this case, 65% of the respondents who indicated that professionals were working towards the same goals, 64.7% said professionals shared information with them about their children, and 64% believed that professionals have effective knowledge of collaboration. More than half of the respondents (55.1%) indicated that professionals were willing to train them.

Equality

Items 18-21 show the respondents' perceptions of being treated as equals when collaborating with professionals.

Table 5: *Items Related to Equality*

Rank	Survey Item	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Very Frequently	Always
18	Professionals listen to and use the information I provide for decision-making.	7.4%	12.1%	30.9%	31.3%	18.4%
19	Professionals respect my input and my contributions to the agreed-upon goals for my child.	7.7%	11.4%	29.8%	31.6%	19.5%
20	Professionals are willing to adjust their roles and responsibilities to meet the goals established for my child.	11.4%	18.0%	34.2%	22.4%	13.9%
21	Conflicts between professionals and parents are resolved smoothly.	6.6%	11.8%	30.9%	31.6%	19.1%

Most of the respondents' answers were “occasionally” and “very frequently” and in close proportions. When respondents were asked about the professionals' listening skills and use of information provided by families, 31.3% of them replied “very frequently” and 30.9% “occasionally”. Likewise, 31.6% of the respondents indicated that professionals “very frequently” listen and respect parental input, whereas “occasionally” was the choice of 29.8%, and “always” the option of 19.5%. According to the 34.2% of the respondents, professionals were “occasionally” willing to adjust their roles and responsibilities, while 22.4% believe that they “very frequently” adjust their roles to meet the goals established for their children. Finally, 31.6% of the respondents selected “very frequently” regarding the item conflicts between professionals and parents being resolved smoothly, while “occasionally” was chosen by 30.9% and “always” by 19.1% of respondents.

Trust and Respect

A 5-point Likert scale was used to present the data on these survey items (see Table 6).

Table 6: Items Related to Trust and Respect

Rank	Survey Item	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Very Frequently	Always
22	Professionals take their responsibilities toward my child's and family's needs seriously.	9.9%	9.2%	24.6%	37.5%	18.8%
23	Professionals take the time to develop a relationship with my family and me.	11.4%	17.3%	31.3%	24.7%	15.4%
24	Professionals' respect and accept my opinions and decisions.	5.1%	10.7%	37.5%	25.0%	21.7%
25	My decisions are valued by professionals.	8.8%	8.8%	36.0%	26.8%	19.5%

Regarding the item concerning professionals taking their responsibilities seriously, “very frequently” was the choice of 37.5% of the respondents, with “occasionally” chosen by 24.6%, and “always” chosen by 18.8%. Moreover, 31.3% of the respondents reported that professionals “occasionally” take the time to develop a relationship with families, while 24.7% and 17.3% stated “rarely”. About a one-third (37.5%) of the respondents reported that professionals “occasionally” respect and accept parents' opinions and decisions, and the breakdown of responses was: “very frequently” at 25.0%, and “always” at 21.7%. Finally, 36.8% of respondents indicated professionals “occasionally” value families' decisions, with “very frequently” being the choice of 26.8% and “always” being chosen by 19.5%.

Relationships Between Demographic Variables and Responses

To determine the differences concerning gender variable, 72.1% female ($n = 196$) and 27.9% male ($n = 76$), independent sample t -tests were conducted. One-way ANOVA was utilized to determine whether there were any statistical differences related to (a) educational level achieved by parents; (b) income level; (c) degree of severity of child's disability; and (d) type of early intervention center. One-way ANOVA was used to determine the differences, if any, between three or more groups.

Table 7: Differences related to educational achievements, socioeconomic status, intervention centers and disability severity

Educational Achievement	Source of Variance	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Knowledge of Practices	SS Between	3	1.31	3.095	0.027
	SS within	268	0.423		
Communication	SS Between	3	0.614	0.84	0.473
	SS within	268	0.731		
Commitment	SS Between	3	0.743	0.807	0.491
	SS within	268	0.92		
Equality	SS Between	3	1.069	1.111	0.345
	SS within	268	0.962		
Trust & Respect	SS Between	3	1.135	1.038	0.376
	SS within	268	1.093		
Socioeconomic Status	SS Between	3	0.029	0.067	0.977
	SS within	265	0.434		

Communication	SS Between	3	0.088	0.118	0.949
	SS within	265	0.741		
Commitment	SS Between	3	0.629	0.685	0.562
	SS within	265	0.919		
Equality	SS Between	3	0.307	0.317	0.813
	SS within	265	0.967		
Trust & Respect	SS Between	3	0.762	0.696	0.555
	SS within	265	1.095		
Intervention Centers					
Knowledge of Practices	SS Between	1	0.024	0.055	0.815
	SS within	270	0.434		
Communication	SS Between	1	6.294	8.883	0.003
	SS within	270	0.709		
Commitment	SS Between	1	6.099	6.785	0.01
	SS within	270	0.899		
Equality	SS Between	1	6.746	7.164	0.008
	SS within	270	0.942		
Trust & Respect	SS Between	1	3.407	3.14	0.078
	SS within	270	1.085		
Disability severity		SS	DF	MS	F
Knowledge of Practices	SS Between	0.73	2	0.365	0.842
	SS within	116.604	269	0.433	
Communication	SS Between	1.948	2	0.974	1.339
	SS within	195.672	269	0.727	
Commitment	SS Between	1.017	2	0.508	0.552
	SS within	247.799	269	0.921	
Equality	SS Between	2.116	2	1.058	1.099
	SS within	258.883	269	0.962	
Trust & Respect	SS Between	4.599	2	2.300	2.12
	SS within	291.734	269	1.085	

Note. Significant difference is $p < .05$.

Table (7) shows the statistically significant differences attributed to educational achievement for knowledge of practices [$F(3, 268) = 3.09, p = .02$]. It also indicates that the level of education is insignificant for communication [$F(3, 268) = .94, p = .47$], commitment [$F(3, 268) = .807, p = .49$], equality [$F(3, 268) = 1.11, p = .34$], and trust and respect [$F(3, 268) = 1.03, p = .37$]. Monthly income was not found to correlate with parents' perceptions ($p < .05$) regarding any of the variables. Findings also indicated no statistically significant difference ascribed to the type of centers for knowledge of practices [$F(1, 270) = .055, p = .81$] and trust and respect [$F(1, 270) = 3.140, p = .07$].

However, there were significant differences between groups attributable to the type of early intervention center for the variables: communication [$F(1, 270) = 8.883, p = .00$], commitment [$F(1, 270) = 6.785, p = .01$], and equality [$F(1, 270) = 7.164, p = .00$]. Finally, the severity of a child's disability was not deemed significant for all five variables ($p < .05$).

Interviews with Parents

All of the six interviewees were female with an undergraduate educational achievement. Four of them defined their families as middle class and two as upper class. Every interviewee exhibited an understanding of the importance of early childhood special education services and expressed a desire for seeing improvement in these. Their responses were analyzed descriptively by utilizing the thematic content analysis method. This involved coding the data and categorizing them into interrelated themes (Saldaña, 2013).

When parents were asked, "How would you define collaboration?" as many as 33.3% said "working toward a mutual goal" while (16.6%) considered it "widely beneficial and should include: children, parents, teachers, and even the community." Furthermore, (16.6%) said "it involves providing help for people who are in need, and it requires attending meetings to discuss the child's abilities." When parents were asked about effective collaboration, 16.6% stated "professionals and parents should understand the difficulties that families encounter, including psychological or behavioral, and even physical fatigue." Regarding the experience that affects their perceptions, the majority of the interviewees stated they have had not been given clear guidance on their role or how they can participate in activities. Of these, 16.66% reported a positive experience and 83.33% were dissatisfied with their experiences. For example, Parents 5, 6 and 4 stated that the center preferred to work without the families' involvement.

Concerning the factors promoting collaboration, 66.66% of the interviewees said the availability of services and the humanity of professionals, while 16.6% stated raising awareness at the early stages of a child's life, and being honest. Many parents (1, 3, 4 and 5) identified another factor which is the level of training for both parents and professionals. Moreover, when they were asked about the factors that hinder collaboration, two parents (3 and 5) emphasized that the socioeconomic status and work schedules of the family occupy a vital role. Three parents (1, 3 and 6) believed that parental awareness concerning the child's disability is very important. Parent 6 highlighted the fact that, "There is a lack of families' voices" and that more regulations and services should be provided for their children.

Discussion

The Saudi parents' perception regarding of the reality of collaboration and obstacles which hinder its productive implementation was examined by employing a meta-inference approach method. The mean score for all respondents (n=272) was $M=3.60$, $SD=.74$, meaning that most respondents either chose "occasionally" or "very frequently". Furthermore, five parents (83.3 %) reported indicated a positive view of collaboration during the interview. Briefly, both the survey and the interview results indicate the parents' eagerness to collaborate with educational professionals. This finding is attributed to the fact that this subject is understudied in Saudi Arabia.

The results for knowledge of collaboration practices show that parents have an adequate understanding of collaboration practices because most of their replies were "strongly agreed" or "somewhat agreed." As previously stated in the findings section, 76.8 % had sufficient awareness of collaborative practices. Similarly, in the interview, four interviewees (66%) agreed that collaboration is very beneficial and helps both parents and children. This result could be ascribed to private and governmental efforts to increase the involvement of families with children with special needs in ECSE as well as their determination to enhance the children's academic performance by fostering collaboration. This result is consistent with the results of (Tucker & Schwartz, 2013) which indicated that 71% of parents had "high" participation in the educational process and 23 % "moderate". This also coincides with the results of (Tucker & Schwartz, 2013).

Regarding communication practices, over 62% of respondents said communication was not clear, and that the remainder of the parents (36.8 % occasionally, 10.7 % rarely, and 5.1 % never) believe that professionals' communication skills need to be improved. This is consistent with the majority of the interviewees' responses which indicated that professionals need more training in order to improve enhance their communication skills. This result could be attributed to the lack of preparation that professionals receive. Additionally, it could be ascribed to the language barriers as nearly (20%-30%) of the professionals in EI centers are not Saudis which may lead to missing subtle communication cues.

Concerning professionals' commitment, 49.6% of respondents chose "always" or "very frequently" for the item "professionals are working toward the same goals" while 47.8% indicated professionals effectively shared information. Similarly, parents in the interview stated that a mutual target requires that professionals treat their children as "more than just a case." These results are consistent with the findings of (Tucker & Schwartz, 2013). This result could be ascribed to a lack of preparation obtained by professionals.

The findings of equality indicate that 63.7% of the respondents had low perceptions of professionals' attitudes toward equality in collaboration with families in ECSE in Saudi Arabia. Likewise, five interviewees mentioned that professionals impose their opinions and decisions on the process. These findings coincide with previous research (Kyzar et al., 2019; Murray et al., 2013).

This result reveals that about 53.3% of the respondents did not feel that professionals had a sufficient level of trust and respect toward them in collaboration. Most of the interviewees stated they had not been given clear guidance on their role in collaboration and on when they can and should participate in activities. These findings could be ascribed to the professionals' need for more training in collaboration with parents, and how to earn their trust and respect. The findings are consistent with the results of (Blue-Banning et al., 2004).

Regarding factors promoting collaboration, six Saudi parents revealed that collaboration is promoted by the availability of services and the humanity of professionals. This finding is consistent with what (Blue-Banning et al, 2004) provided as examples and guidance on factors and practices that promote successful collaboration between families and professionals in early childhood special education. The second theme is the level of parents/professionals training which is consistent with the results of (Kyzar et al., 2016 and Majoko, 2017). This finding agrees with Saudi Government initiatives for developing special education as it supports and funds various programs which serve children with disabilities. Nevertheless, parents indicated two major hurdles to collaboration which are the socioeconomic level and parental awareness. This result is also consistent with (Simpson & Envy, 2015) who revealed how crucial socioeconomic status may impact educational distribution.

Limitations

The results of this study may be influenced by response biases as any other study. Participants may have preferred to overreport their awareness of behaviors. To reduce social desirability bias, the researcher assured all participants that their responses were anonymous and encoded and would not harm them. Generalizability is also limited because of the delivery method. The participants of this study were limited to those who had an Internet connection. Conclusions drawn from this study may not apply to other subsamples of parents. Also, the survey was translated from English to Arabic, meaning that, respondents may misinterpret some items due to language differences. One of the most important limitations was the distance between the interviewer and the interviewees such as (difficulty in communicating with parents across time zones and expense).

Recommendations

In view of the findings of this study, the researcher recommends:

- Conducting more research to investigate the reality of the implementation of collaboration between educational professionals and parents of children with disabilities in KSA;
- Researching parents' needs in early intervention;
- Enacting more laws that define how to undertake successful collaboration in ECSE to obtain the best outcomes for children with disabilities education;
- Providing more training programs to strengthen collaborative practices (parents and professionals) in early education settings.

Conclusion

This study employed a mixed-method design to identify the reality of collaboration practices between parents of children with disabilities and education professionals in ECSE from parents' perspectives in Saudi Arabia. The results of both qualitative and quantitative methods showed that equality, trust, commitment, knowledge of practice and communication are important attributes that affect collaboration between Saudi parents and professionals. The findings also showed **significant differences ascribed to** educational achievement for knowledge of practices. However, there were no significant differences attributed to monthly income, type of intervention centers or the severity of the child's disability.

References

- Almalki, N. (2013). *Professional development needs of early intervention providers of preschoolers with moderate and severe disabilities in Saudi Arabia* (Doctoral dissertation). Retrieved from <http://cardinalscholar.bsu.edu/handle/123456789/197775>.
- Alquraini, T. (2013). Legislative rules for students with disabilities in the United States and Saudi Arabia: A comparative study. *International Interdisciplinary Journal of Education*, 2(6), 601-614. doi:10.12816/0002942
- Al-Zoubi, S. M., & Rahman, M. S. B. A. (2015). Mainstreaming in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: Obstacles facing learning disabilities resource room. *Journal of Studies in Education*, 6(1), 37-55. doi:10.5296/jse.v6i1.8800
- Bang, Y.-S. (2018). Parents' perspectives on how their behaviours impede parent-teacher collaboration. *Social Behavior and Personality*, 46(11), 1787-1799. doi:10.2224/sbp.7270
- Blackmore, R., Aylward, E., & Grace, R. (2016). 'One of the kids': Parents' perceptions of the developmental advantages arising from inclusion in mainstream early childhood education services. *Australasian Journal of Early Childhood*, 41(2), 13-17. doi:10.1177/183693911604100203
- Blue-Banning, M., Summers, J. A., Frankland, H. C., Nelson, L. L., & Beegle, G. B. (2004). Dimensions of family and professional partnerships: Constructive guidelines for collaboration. *Exceptional Children*, 70(2), 167-184. doi:10.1177/001440290407000203
- Brock, M. E., Cannella-Malone, H. I., Seaman, R. L., Andzik, N. R., Schaefer, J. M., Page, E. J., ... Dueker, S. A. (2017). Findings across practitioner training studies in special education: A comprehensive review and meta-analysis. *Exceptional Children*, 84(1), 7-26. doi:10.1177/0014402917698008
- Clough, P., & Nutbrown, C. (2019). Exploring the place of arts-based approaches in early childhood education research. *Journal of Early Childhood Research*, 17(1), 3-13. doi:10.1177/1476718X19834220
- Dare, L., Nowicki, E., Felimban, H. (2017). Saudi children's thoughts on inclusive education. *International Journal on Inclusive Education*, 21(5), 532-543. doi:10.1080/13603116.2016.1218948
- Felimban, H. (2019). Considerations for delivering culturally informed early intervention services in Saudi Arabia. In S. Acar, H. Hix-Small, & T. McLaughlin (Eds.), *Young exceptional children monograph series No.18* (pp. 74- 88). Washington, DC: Division for Early Childhood.
- Friend, M., & Cook, L. (2014). *Interactions: Collaboration skills for school professionals* (7th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson Education Limited.

- Hadidi, M. S., & Alkhateeb, J. M. (2020). *Early intervention: Early childhood special education*. Amman, Jordan: Dar Alfiker.
- Hamilton-Jones, B. M., & Vail, C. O. (2014). Preparing special educators for collaboration in the classroom: Pre-service teachers' beliefs and perspectives. *International Journal of Special Education*, 29(1), 76-86. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ11034079.pdf>.
- Hernandez, S. J. (2013). Collaboration in special education: Its history, evolution, and critical factors necessary for successful implementation [Online Submission]. *US-China Education Review*, 3(6), 480-498.
- Hopkins, L., Lorains, J., Issaka, A., & Podbury, R. (2017). How does 'community' facilitate early childhood service use in a multicultural Australian suburb? *Journal of Early Childhood Research*, 15(1), 3-16. doi:10.1177/1476718X14552876
- Kyzar, K., Brady, S., Summers, J., Haines, S., & Turnbull, A. (2016). Services and supports, partnership, and family quality of life: Focus on deaf blindness. *Exceptional Children*, 83(1), 77-91. doi:10.1177/0014402916655432
- Kyzar, K. B., Mueller, T. G., Francis, G. L., & Haines, S. J. (2019). Special education teacher preparation for family-professional partnerships: Results from a national survey of teacher educators. *Teacher Education and Special Education*, 42(4), 320-337. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0888406419839123>
- Lohman, M., Hathcote, A. R., & Hogan, K. A. (2018). Addressing the barriers to family-school collaboration: A brief review of the literature and recommendations for practice. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 10(1), 26-32. doi:10.20489/intjecse.454424
- Majoko, T. (2017). Practices that support the inclusion of children with an autism spectrum disorder in mainstream early childhood education in Zimbabwe. *SAGE Open*, 7(3), 1-10. doi:10.1177/2158244017730387
- Meadan, H., & Daczewitz, M. E. (2014). Internet-based intervention training for parents of young children with disabilities: A promising service-delivery model. *Early Child Development and Care*, 185(1), 155-169. Routledge. doi:10.1080/03004430.2014.908866
- Murry, F. R., & Alqahtani, R. M. A. (2015). Teaching special education law in Saudi Arabia: Improving pre-service teacher education and services to students with disabilities. *World Journal of Education*, 5(6), 57-64. doi:10.5430/wje.v5n6p57
- Murray, M., Handyside, L., Straka, L., & Arton-Titus, T. (2013). Parent Empowerment: Connecting with Preservice Special Education Teachers. *School Community Journal*, 23(1), 145-168. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com/docview/1406196548/>.
- Paananen, M., Lipponen, L., & Kumpulainen, K. (2015). Hybridisation or ousterisation? The case of local accountability policy in Finnish early childhood education. *European Educational Research Journal*, 14(5), 395-417. doi:10.1177/1474904115601446
- Sabol, T. J., Sommer, T. E., Sanchez, A., & Busby, A. K. (2018). A new approach to defining and measuring family engagement in early childhood education programs. *AERA Open*, 4(3), 1-10. doi:10.1177/2332858418785904
- Schultz, T. R., Sreckovic, M. A., Able, H., & White, T. (2016). Parent-teacher collaboration: Teacher perceptions of what is needed to support students with ASD in the inclusive classroom. *Education and Training in Autism and Developmental Disabilities*, 51(4), 344-354.
- Simpson, D., & Envy, R. (2015). Subsidizing early childhood education and care for parents on a low income: Moving beyond the individualized economic rationale of neoliberalism. *Contemporary Issues in Early Childhood*, 16(2), 166-178. doi:10.1177/1463949115585673
- Summers, J. A., Hoffman, L., Marquis, J., Turnbull, A., Poston, D., & Nelson, L. L. (2005). Measuring the quality of family—Professional partnerships in special education services. *Exceptional Children*, 72(1), 65-81. doi:10.1177/001440290507200104
- Tucker, V., & Schwartz, I. (2013). Parents' Perspectives of Collaboration with School Professionals: Barriers and Facilitators to Successful Partnerships in Planning for Students with ASD. *School Mental Health*, 5(1), 3-14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12310-012-9102-0>
- Turnbull, A., Turnbull, H. R., Erwin, E. J., Soodak, L. C., & Shogren, K. A. (2015). *Families, professionals, and exceptionality: Positive outcomes through partnership and trust* (7th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Education.
- Viviani, M. (2016). Creating dialogues: Exploring the 'good early childhood educator' in Chile. *Contemporary Issues in Early Childhood*, 17(1), 92-105. doi:10.1177/1463949115627906
- Yell, M. (2019). *The law and special education* (5th ed.). New York, NY: Pearson.
- Young, A. J. (2017). *Effect of adapted physical education and homework on gross motor development for young children with Down Syndrome* (Doctoral dissertation). Available from ProQuest Dissertations Publishing. Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/openview/5ded8b57e4c8de1b5590d8df19aa2b7d/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>.

Author Information

Mohamad Bukhary
University Of Jeddah
Jeddah, Saudi Arabia
